

Semantic Modelling for Representation and Integration of Health Data from Wearable Devices

Theodora Tasia¹, Christoniki Maga-Nteve²[0000-0002-1242-691X], Nikos Tsolakis²[0000-0002-5490-553X], Georgios Meditskos¹[0000-0003-4242-5245], Thanassis Mavropoulos²[0000-0002-7326-5910], and Stefanos Vrochidis²[0000-0002-2505-9178]

¹ School of Informatics, Aristotle University of Thessaloniki,
54124, Thessaloniki, Greece
{theodtasia,gmeditsk}@csd.auth.gr

² Information Technologies Institute, Centre for Research and Technology Hellas,
57001, Thessaloniki, Greece
{chmaga,tsolakin,mavrathan,stefanos}@iti.gr

Abstract. The efficient sharing and integration of health-related data are critical objectives in the rapidly developing field of healthcare technology. In order to achieve this, a seamless exchange of health information across different frameworks is needed, promoting interoperability among health data formats, a key factor in the progression of digital health solutions. In this paper, we present our work in defining and implementing a mapping between the Fast Healthcare Interoperability Resources (FHIR) standard and the Open mHealth (OMH) schema, two well-known and widely used solutions for health-related data modeling. We elaborate on key mapping choices that have been made to conceptually align the two paradigms, and we present examples that demonstrate the applicability of our approach. The contribution to the research community is marked by advancements in interoperability and the facilitation of seamless integration across diverse health data formats. Also, the potential impact is significant, offering benefits to both healthcare professionals and the patients under their care.

Keywords: Open mHealth · FHIR · RDF · Interoperability.

1 Introduction

The notion of health data management systems has undergone transformation over the past century [1]. As the world faces global health crises like the COVID-19 pandemic, the significance of standards for effective health data management is emphasized [2]. The majority of recently branded mobile health (mHealth) apps rely on pandemic response features such as early diagnosis, symptom detection, and intrusive contact tracing. [3]. Due to their ubiquitous presence,

connectivity, and multitude of built-in sensors, mobile phones and other technologies can be seamlessly integrated into daily life to aid in the prevention and management of chronic illnesses [4]. As the use of mobile devices for health tracking grows, a vast volume of healthcare data is generated daily. However, the potential of these data is not fully exploited due to challenges in standardization and interoperability.

Interoperability in healthcare systems ensures comprehensive patient care and efficient information exchange. This flexibility to adjust to technological advancements improves patient involvement and research capacities, while also lowering costs throughout the healthcare system. The absence of widespread interoperability is frequently identified as a notable drawback in the existing Electronic Health Records (EHRs), leading to duplicated healthcare expenses, increased fatigue among clinicians, and presenting a potential threat to patient safety [5]. Interoperability in clinical data demands shared specifications for meaningful understanding [6]. Standardization in healthcare is vital for establishing uniform protocols, formats, and practices, ensuring consistency and enhancing data accuracy, communication, and coordinated patient care. Open mHealth (OMH) is recognized as a key standard for health data interoperability across apps, mobile devices, and platforms. It is essential for comprehending a diverse array of patient-generated information [7].

Facilitating seamless connections between disparate health information standards is essential for maximizing the potential of mHealth data. HL7's FHIR [8], the industry standard for healthcare data exchange, was developed incrementally, reflecting current best practices in complex systems architecture [9]. Integrating standards such as OMH and FHIR enhances interoperability, fostering effective communication among diverse health data sources for comprehensive patient care, research, and healthcare management.

This paper introduces an extensible mapping approach to facilitate the development of an FHIR to OMH standard data mapping tool. The main purposes of this mapping tool are to: 1) ensure adaptability to a wide range of health data types, 2) comprehensively represent diverse health information, promoting clarity and coherence in the mapped data output, 3) enhance interoperability across different wearable and IoT devices. The rest of this paper is structured as follows. Section 2 discusses the related work, providing an overview of existing works in the field of methodological reuse of technologies. Section 3 delves into the methodology adopted for the mapping process. In Section 4, the paper elaborates on the mapping tool workflow, providing a detailed description of the tool's operation through a practical example. Finally, Section 5 serves as the conclusion, summarizing the key points discussed in the paper and presenting future work considerations.

2 Related Work

Interoperability issues have gained attention in the field of health information systems, where standards are increasingly utilized by both developers and health-

care providers to enhance data interchange [10]. Numerous studies have focused on achieving semantic interoperability in clinical annotations and health records as this effort continues, highlighting the necessity for innovative tools and integration strategies.

Georgy Kopanitsa et al. address interoperability challenges between hospital information systems (HIS) and clinical decision support systems (CDSS), by proposing an approach that utilizes archetypes as a standardized mechanism. This enables CDSSs to collect and reuse medical data from various institutions without requiring modifications in the implementation [11]. Furthermore, the introduction of a Structure Mapping Service in the CrowdHEALTH project, as outlined by Lete et al. [12], employs ontology alignment to automate the process and seamlessly integrate healthcare settings. This provides a comprehensive solution to enhance interoperability and bridge the gap in information exchange.

Additionally, V. Gay and P. Leijdekkers [13] illustrate the effective utilization of a mobile application to aggregate health and fitness data, showcasing its capability to facilitate interoperability. Moreover, the Smart Data Models Program facilitates robust data exchange across organizations by providing openly licensed shared data models, adhering to agile standardization principles. The NGS standard, integral to various domains including health, presents a standardized, REST-compatible format for data requests across diverse systems [14].

A reference data model for Living Labs (LL) research, was proposed by Maganteve et al. [15], leveraging existing schemas from the OMH Standard library. Its main goal is to provide an adaptable data model that guarantees standard representation formats for information shared throughout Living Labs by creating a globally accepted schema. Additionally, a toolkit was developed, encompassing a fundamental semantic model functioning as its knowledge base and a versatile framework for integrating semantic data was developed [16]. Notably, this semantic framework employs health standards for interpreting health data.

An important guide was developed to illustrate the integration of OmH with FHIR, playing a crucial role in the development of the mapping tool proposed in this research. This guide enables the retrieval of health data from prominent third-party APIs such as Google Fit. Subsequently, the acquired data is made accessible to an FHIR SMART client, presented either in the native Open mHealth schema format or as FHIR resources like Observations. This seamless accessibility is facilitated through the OmH Shimmer application and the server Open mHealth to FHIR, both of which play crucial roles in the development of this paper [17].

3 Methodology

In this section, the foundations are set to present the methodology employed in the mapping procedure. The mapping methodology is unquestionably a critical component of this research, serving as a vital link in facilitating a smooth transition between the FHIR and OMH standards.

Table 1. OMH and FHIR Properties Mapping

OMH Properties	FHIR Properties
	Observation.
General Health Metrics, Fitness / Oxygen-related / Activity Metrics, Device / System Information & Descriptive Statistics, Measurement Method & Sensor Information, Blood Pressure	code
Physical Activity / Cardiovascular / Physiological Metrics, Body Composition / Motion and Movement Metrics	valueQuantity
Time Interval Metrics	effectiveTimeFrame
Temporal Relationship Metrics, Body Posture	component
BodySite	bodySite
id	subject
Specimen Source	reference

In the proposed methodology, we proceeded by meticulously analyzing OMH data schemas, exploring various aspects of their structure, representation, and the variety of health-related data they contain. This thorough investigation included the analysis of data types, the hierarchical structure of the OMH schemas, and the particular health metrics they encompass, such as heart rate measurements, physical activity data, and other relevant variables.

Subsequently, we engaged in a thorough exploration of the FHIR ontology, gaining profound insights into its conceptual framework. This involved a comprehensive examination of FHIR's core concepts, data structures, and semantic representations, enabling us to understand the complex relationships between various health-related entities within the FHIR standard. This meticulous process, combined with the utilization of mFHIR, laid the groundwork for a comprehensive mapping methodology.

The systematic identification of key features of OMH, such as recurring elements like "effective time frame" and "descriptive statistics", highlights a purposeful commitment to precise data mapping and representation. This methodical effort employs a strategic grouping approach, organizing the mapping process into distinct groups. This deliberate grouping not only facilitates a more coherent and systematic mapping methodology but also contributes to the development of reusable mapping techniques. By aligning these features with the FHIR standard, this group-based mapping method becomes an essential cornerstone, guaranteeing a unified and reusable approach to health data management within the expansive open mHealth ecosystem.

Table 1 provides a clear illustration of the mapping methodology used to align OMH schema attributes with the FHIR standard. Additionally, it highlights the systematic and structured nature of these mapping relationships by grouping OMH attributes, thereby facilitating enhanced comprehension and organizational coherence. Collectively, these components highlight the meticulous and effective mapping process used to ensure a logical synthesis between OMH schemas and the FHIR standard. In Fig. 1, an example is presented, particularly highlighting the acceleration schema within the OMH framework. By delving into this specific schema, we gain a nuanced understanding of the practical application of the

```

{
  "acceleration_x": {
    "value": 0.0596923828125,
    "unit": "m/s^2"
  },
  "acceleration_y": {
    "value": 0.0125,
    "unit": "m/s^2"
  },
  "acceleration_z": {
    "value": 0.0001,
    "unit": "m/s^2"
  },
  "id": "Jonh_k_323",
  "sensor_body_location": "right wrist",
  "effective_time_frame": {
    "date_time": "2015-08-18T07:25:00Z"
  },
  "descriptive_statistic": "average"
}

```

Fig. 1. Accelerator Schema

mapping technique. The provided schema captures the structure and properties needed to record accelerometer readings, displayed in JSON format. This schema illustrates three-dimensional acceleration data containing significant parameters such as "acceleration_x", "acceleration_y", and "acceleration_z", each corresponding to a specific value and unit. To ensure a comprehensive representation of accelerometer measurements, the schema includes additional properties such as "id", "sensor_body_location", "effective_time_frame", and "descriptive_statistic". The parameters "acceleration_x", "acceleration_y", and "acceleration_z", correspond to the three axes of the coordinate system ("x" representing the horizontal axis, "y" the vertical axis, and "z" the depth axis). The "id" attribute serves to uniquely identify the patient's data entry, while the location of the accelerometer sensor on the body (in this case, the right wrist) is specified by the "sensor_body_location" element. The timestamp for the accelerometer readings was obtained from the "effective_time_frame", and the statistical measure (in this case, "average") was specified by the "descriptive_statistic".

The structured format of Table 2 provides a systematic breakdown of how each OMH property of the above accelerometer schema aligns with corresponding FHIR components, specifying FHIR codes, systems, and data types. Each row corresponds to data attributes like acceleration in x, y, and z directions, a unique identifier (id), sensor body location, date and time, and descriptive statistics. The attributes "acceleration_x", "acceleration_y", and "acceleration_z" align with FHIR components in "Observation.component", the "id" attribute maps to "Observation.subject.Patient.identifier", and "sensor_body_location" corresponds to "Observation.bodySite" in FHIR. The "effective_time_frame" attribute is mapped to "Observation.effectiveTimeFrame", and the "descriptive_statistics" property in the OMH schema is appropriately aligned with "Observation.code".

Table 2. Accelerometer Data Mapping

OMH	FHIR	Value	Type
acceleration_x	Observation.component[0].code.coding[0].code	ACCELERATION_X	code
	Observation.component[0].code.coding[0].system	omh_fhir_codes	string
	Observation.component[0].valueQuantity	-	Quantity
	Observation.component[0].valueQuantity.value	0.0596923828125	decimal
	Observation.component[0].valueQuantity.unit	m/s ²	string
acceleration_y	Observation.component[1].code.coding[0].code	ACCELERATION_Y	code
	Observation.component[1].code.coding[0].system	omh_fhir_codes	string
	Observation.component[1].valueQuantity	-	Quantity
	Observation.component[1].valueQuantity.value	0.0125	decimal
	Observation.component[1].valueQuantity.unit	m/s ²	string
acceleration_z	Observation.component[2].code.coding[0].code	ACCELERATION_Z	code
	Observation.component[2].code.coding[0].system	omh_fhir_codes	string
	Observation.component[2].valueQuantity	-	Quantity
	Observation.component[2].valueQuantity.value	0.0001	decimal
	Observation.component[2].valueQuantity.unit	m/s ²	string
id	Observation.subject	-	Patient
	Observation.subject.Patient.identifier	Jonh_k_323	string
sensor_body_location	Observation.bodySite	-	-
	Observation.bodySite.coding[0].code	right_wrist	code
	Observation.bodySite.coding[0].system	CodeSystem_body_location	string
	Observation.bodySite.coding[0].display	RIGHT_WIRST	string
effective_date_time	Observation.effectiveDateTime	2015-08-18T07:25:00Z	dateTime
descriptive_statistic	Observation.code.coding[1].code	average	code
	Observation.code.coding[1].display	AVERAGE	string
	Observation.code.coding[1].system	omh_fhir_observation_codes	string

4 Mapping Tool

The mapping methodology forms the foundational framework that enables the development and utilization of the mapping tool. This tool is implemented in Java using the RDF4J framework. The repository for this project can be found on GitHub at [OMH_TO_FHIR](#).

4.1 Workflow

The tool simplifies the integration process by receiving a user-provided folder containing JSON files, that adhere specifically to OMH data schemas. These schemas can be selectively chosen based on different health data types, exemplified by categories like heart rate. Currently, the tool covers approximately 70% of OMH schemas, excluding enumerations and Apple HealthKit schemas. However, it is designed to be easily extensible, allowing for the seamless extension of coverage to include additional schemas as needed. This user-centered approach empowers individuals to tailor the integration process to their specific needs, ensuring a personalized and efficient workflow.

Upon receiving the user's selected folder, the tool initiates an intuitive menu interface, guiding users through the mapping process. Users can categorize the selected schemas, making it easier to modify data in a more focused and context-aware manner. This feature of the tool enhances usability and ensures that the mapping processes align with the distinctive qualities of the integrated health data.

The mapping tool excels in its ability to convert OMH JSON data to the FHIR standard seamlessly. Following the mapping process, it creates unique Turtle files for every JSON file, encapsulating the mapped data in an FHIR-compatible Resource Description Framework (RDF) [18] format. The RDF format facilitates the communication of health data in a more organized, interoperable manner while also improving data representation.

The program uses the Shapes Constraint Language (SHACL) [19] for validation to further guarantee data integrity and conformity to predetermined criteria. To ensure consistency and reliability throughout the integration process, the mapped data must match the expected structures and limitations described by the FHIR standard.

Fig. 2. Mapping Tool Workflow

In addition to data validation, the tool empowers users by providing the capability to perform SPARQL [20] queries on the integrated and validated data within the GraphDB. This feature enables users to extract meaningful insights from the integrated datasets, fostering a structured and interoperable approach for handling diverse Open mHealth data schemas mapped to the FHIR standard. This workflow is visually represented in Figure 2, providing a clear depiction of the described process.

4.2 Heart Rate Mapping Example

To visually represent the results generated by the tool, we employ the schema designed for heart rate observations. The JSON structure of the heart rate is elucidated in Figure 3, providing a comprehensive visualization of the tool's output.

Figure 4, illustrates the transformation of the heart rate value (75 beats/min) and its unit (beats/min) into an FHIR Quantity datatype. Additionally, it demonstrates the representation of patient information using the FHIR Patient resource, identified by the unique identifier "Jonh_K_12."

The detailed breakdown of the heart rate observation mappings provides a comprehensive insight into the analytical mapping process. Each component is transformed and encoded to ensure a meaningful representation within the FHIR framework. The following enumerates key aspects of this mapping:

```

{
  "heart_rate": {
    "value": 75,
    "unit": "beats/min"
  },
  "id": "Jonh_K_12",
  "descriptive_statistic": "average",
  "temporal_relationship_to_physical_activity": "before exercise",
  "temporal_relationship_to_sleep": "before sleeping"
}

```

Fig. 3. Heart Rate Example

```

fhir_instance:heart_rate_Jonh_K_12 a fhir:Observation;
  fhir:Observation.code fhir_instance:Coding_8867-4, fhir_instance:code_descriptive_statistic_2;
  fhir:Observation.valueQuantity fhir_instance:Quantity0;
  fhir:Observation.subject fhir_instance:Patient_Jonh_K_12;
  fhir:Observation.component fhir_instance:component_temporal_relationship_to_physical_activity_3,
    fhir_instance:component_temporal_relationship_to_sleep_4 .

fhir_instance:Coding_8867-4 fhir:code fhir_instance:8867-4;
  fhir:display fhir_instance:Heart_rate;
  fhir:system fhir_instance:loinc .

fhir_instance:75 a fhir:decimal .
fhir_instance:Quantity0 a fhir:Quantity;
  fhir:Quantity.value fhir_instance:75;
  fhir:Quantity.unit fhir_instance:beats%2Fmin .

fhir_instance:beats%2Fmin a fhir:string .
fhir_instance:Patient_Jonh_K_12 a fhir:Patient;
  fhir:Patient.identifier fhir_instance:Jonh_K_12 .

```

Fig. 4. Quantity and Subject Example

1. **Observation Instance:** The FHIR ‘Observation’ resource represents the heart rate observation for the patient identified as `Jonh_K_12`. It includes details about the code, value quantity, subject (patient), and components related to temporal relationships.
2. **Codeable Concept for Heart Rate:** The LOINC code (8867-4) is represented as a codeable concept with a display name (`Heart_rate`) and a system reference to LOINC.
3. **Quantity for Heart Rate:** The quantity value (75) and unit (`beats/min`) are represented as a FHIR Quantity datatype.
4. **Patient Instance:** The patient information is represented using the FHIR Patient resource, identified by the identifier `Jonh_K_12`.
5. **Codeable Concept for Descriptive Statistic:** The descriptive statistic (`average`) is represented as a codeable concept with a display name (`AVERAGE`) and a system reference.
6. **Codeable Concepts for Temporal Relationships:** Temporal relationships to physical activity (`before exercise`) and sleep (`before sleeping`) are represented as codeable concepts with display names (`BEFORE_EXERCISE` and `BEFORE_SLEEPING`, respectively) and system references.

4.3 SPARQL Exploration

SPARQL is crucial in healthcare data analysis, especially with RDF datasets enriched by standard healthcare ontologies like FHIR. It demonstrates its potency in finding and extracting relevant data by precisely aligning observations with user-specified dates using FHIR language. The query utilizes FHIR vocabulary to select observations with end periods that match specified timestamps, leveraging the enriched RDF dataset for querying and extracting specific observations.

```

PREFIX fhir: <http://hl7.org/fhir/>
PREFIX fhir_instance: <http://hl7.org/fhir_instances/>
PREFIX rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
select ?observation ?end where {
  ?observation a fhir:Observation ;
              fhir:Observation.effectivePeriod ?effectivePeriod .

  ?effectivePeriod fhir:Observation.effectivePeriod.end ?end .
  filter(?end = fhir_instance:2013-02-05T07:35:00Z)
}

```

Fig. 5. SPARQL Example

The output of the SPARQL query displays a set of observations precisely matched with their respective effective end timings, all aligned with the specified timestamp of 2013-02-05T07:35:00Z. Table 3 provides a comprehensive depiction where each row serves as a unique record, illustrating an observation alongside its closely related end time.

Table 3. Observations and Corresponding Effective End Periods

observation	end
heart_rate_The_id_34	2013-02-05T07:35:00Z
blood_glucose_4312	2013-02-05T07:35:00Z
heart_rate_Jonh_K_12	2013-02-05T07:35:00Z

5 Conclusion and Future Work

Despite facing challenges such as rising healthcare costs, long exam wait times, and limited hospital space, the integration of state-of-the-art technology and the widespread use of mobile devices signal a revolutionary era in medicine. Amid these advancements, the pursuit of achieving interoperability in the healthcare domain persists as an ongoing challenge, requiring innovative solutions for seamless data exchange and collaboration across the medical spectrum, while also

advancing standardization practices. To establish a coherent framework spanning heterogeneous healthcare systems and ensure an integrated approach that enhances the overall effectiveness and efficiency of health data administration and communication, standardization is essential.

This paper outlines a methodology for the systematic mapping of OMH data to the FHIR standard. The breakdown of this methodology adds significant value to the field of health informatics by offering a systematic and planned approach to align the various nuances of OMH data with the widely accepted FHIR standard. Additionally, it introduces a specialized mapping tool developed following this methodology. By incorporating this innovative mapping tool into the methodology, the paper not only underscores its practical applicability but also highlights an impactful contribution to healthcare data management, by increasing the efficiency in aligning OMH data with FHIR standards. In particular it 1) guarantees its flexibility to accommodate a broad spectrum of health data types, 2) provides a comprehensive representation of diverse health-related data to foster consistency and 3) increases interoperability throughout an array of wearable devices.

Considering the future research directions, the study proposes exploring the improvement and extension of the mapping procedure to include a wider spectrum of health data sources beyond OMH. This could involve the integration of various health schemas and data types, thereby leading to a more flexible and comprehensive solution. Additionally, future work could delve into the integration of real-world health data directly extracted from wearable devices into the mapping process. This evolution would capture and process live health data streams from wearable devices, enriching the mapping framework and enhancing its applicability to dynamic health scenarios.

Acknowledgements This work has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme under grant agreement No. GA101017558 (ALAMEDA) and the HORIZON-MISS-2022-CANCER-01 project ONCODIR (101104777).

References

1. L. Ismail, H. Materwala, A.P. Karduck, A. Adem, *Requirements of Health Data Management Systems for Biomedical Care and Research: Scoping Review*, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 2020 doi: 10.2196/17508
2. P. K. Dabla, D. Gruson, B. Gouget, S. Bernardini, E. Homsak, *Lessons Learned from the COVID-19 Pandemic: Emphasizing the Emerging Role and Perspectives from Artificial Intelligence, Mobile Health, and Digital Laboratory Medicine*, *EJIFCC*, Volume 32, Number 2, 2021, Pages 224-243, June 29
3. R.S.H. Istepanian, *Mobile Health (m-Health) in Retrospect: The Known Unknowns*, *International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health*, 2022, volume 19, number 7, pages 3747, doi 10.3390/ijerph19073747
4. C. Chen, D. Haddad, J. Selsky, J.E. Hoffman, R.L. Kravitz, D.E. Estrin, I. Sim, *Making Sense of Mobile Health Data: An Open Architecture to Improve Individual-*

- and Population-Level Health, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, 2012, volume 14, number 4, pages e112, doi 10.2196/jmir.2152
5. Roman, L. C., Ancker, J. S., Johnson, S. B., et al. (2017). Navigation in the electronic health record: a review of the safety and usability literature. *Journal of Biomedical Informatics*, 67, 69–79. DOI: 10.1016/j.jbi.2017.01.005.
 6. S. Schulz, R. Stegwee, C. Chronaki, "Standards in Healthcare Data," in Fundamentals of Clinical Data Science, P. Kubben, M. Dumontier, A. Dekker (Eds.), Springer, 2019, Chapter 3. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-99713-1_3.
 7. Open mHealth, *Open mHealth*, 2023, <https://www.openmhealth.org/>, Last accessed on: January 31, 2024
 8. FHIR 2023, <https://www.hl7.org/fhir/>, Last accessed on: January 31, 2024.
 9. D. Bender, K. Sartipi, *HL7 FHIR: An Agile and RESTful Approach to Healthcare Information Exchange*, *Proceedings of the 26th IEEE International Symposium on Computer-Based Medical Systems*, 2013, pages 326-331, doi 10.1109/CBMS.2013.6627810
 10. M. Jaulent, D. Leprovost, J. Charlet, R. Choquet, *Semantic Interoperability Challenges to Process Large Amount of Data: Perspectives in Forensic and Legal Medicine*, *Journal of Forensic and Legal Medicine*, Volume 57, 2018, Pages 19-23, ISSN 1752-928X, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jflm.2016.10.002>.
<https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1752928X1630124X>
 11. G. Kopanitsa, Integration of Hospital Information and Clinical Decision Support Systems to Enable the Reuse of Electronic Health Record Data, *Methods Inf Med*, vol. 56, no. 3, pp. 238-247, May 18, 2017, doi: 10.3414/ME16-01-0057.
 12. S. Aso Lete, C. Caverio, A. Magdalinou, J. Mantas, L. Montandon, Advanced Interoperability Techniques: Structure Mapping Service in CrowdHEALTH Project, *Acta Inform Med*, vol. 28, no. 1, pp. 52-57, Mar 2020.
 13. V. Gay, P. Leijdekkers, *Bringing Health and Fitness Data Together for Connected Health Care: Mobile Apps as Enablers of Interoperability*, *Journal of Medical Internet Research*, Volume 17, Number 11, 2015, Page e260, URL: <https://www.jmir.org/2015/11/e260>, DOI: 10.2196/jmir.5094.
 14. Smart Data Models <https://smartdatamodels.org/> (Accessed on: January 16, 2024)
 15. C. Maga-Nteve, G. Epelde, M. Hernandez, N. Tsolakis, E. Konstantinidis, G. Meditskos, P. Bamidis, S. Vrochidis, *Standardized and extensible reference data model for clinical research in Living Labs*, in *12th International Conference on Current and Future Trends of Information and Communication Technologies in Healthcare (ICTH 2022)*, October 26-28, 2022, Leuven, Belgium.
 16. C. Maga-Nteve, E. Kontopoulos, N. Tsolakis, et al. *A Semantic Technologies Toolkit for Bridging Early Diagnosis and Treatment in Brain Diseases: Report from the Ongoing EU-Funded Research Project ALAMEDA*. In: MTSR 2021, pp. 349-354, 2022
 17. HL7, "HL7 mFHIR," 2024, <https://healthdata1.github.io/mFHIR/>, Last accessed on 2024-31-01.
 18. W3C RDF (Resource Description Framework), *World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)*, <https://www.w3.org/RDF/>
 19. W3C SHACL (Shapes Constraint Language) Specification, *World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)*, <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>
 20. W3C SPARQL 1.1 Query Language Specification, *World Wide Web Consortium (W3C)*, <https://www.w3.org/TR/sparql11-query/>